

Analysis and Implementation of FP-Growth Algorithm to Support Promotion Strategy UNAKI Semarang

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Abstract—The right promotion strategy in promoting higher education is very necessary in addition to introducing about the university, promotions are also carried out to attract the interest and talents of prospective students in continuing to the higher education, especially at UNAKI Semarang. Implementing the Association Rule method and the FP-Growth algorithm in the promotion strategy is the way to find out what right rules or patterns in determining a more accurate promotional strategy. Research used data from prospective students for the last three years, 2016-2018, where in the data the researchers focused more on testing variables or items. The variables used are Region of Origin, Preferred Study Program, previous majors in SMA/SMK, and Parents' Occupation

Keyword-component; *association rules, frequent itemset, FP-Growth algorithm*

I. INTRODUCTION

University is the highest level in the education system in all countries, where the position of university is not much different from elementary school or junior and senior high school. University is just more about deepening the interests, talents, and potential of each person, so that they will be do things better in working world. Along with the times, many universities, both private and state, have even competed with each other in finding students. Various active promotions have been done, such as advertisements on social media, placing billboards, distributing brochures, giving scholarship programs, or collaborating with student courses. Not only facilities and programs that attract interests and talents, job prospects after graduating from university also become a consideration for students in choosing university. Thus, this can be a reference for all universities, especially UNAKI Semarang, on how to find a more accurate promotion strategy.

Through the student data in the last few years, starting from 2016-2018, the number of UNAKI Semarang

students has increased quite significantly. It could be seen from the data that in 2016 UNAKI Semarang accepted 147 new students, in 2017 UNAKI accepted 283 new students, and in 2018 UNAKI accepted 385 new students. This was also a burden for UNAKI Semarang to maintain the number of students according to the target that have been set for the following years. Several promotional activities have been carried out by UNAKI, such as going directly to the community to provide information and the programs offered. These promotional activities were carried out not only in the Semarang City, but also in another cities and provinces. Those activities required a large amount of funds. Hopefully, this large amount of funds was in line with the target of UNAKI Semarang's new students. To determine the right promotional goals and targets were not easy, there were several factors that had to be reviewed before carrying out targeted promotional activities, such as different student hometowns, previous majors in SMA/SMK which are the benchmarks in determining which majors are will be taken in university, as well as the parents' jobs and income.

The new student data were one of the data sources that could be used. Since until right now, the available new student data was only stored without any further processing. In this case, data mining opened up opportunities for a more effective management of educational strategies. Data mining could explore the added value of a data set into a new, unknown knowledge so far [1]. Research on university promotion strategies has been carried out with several different algorithms. Research [2] used the K-Means algorithm in processing and analyzing data on students who have graduated or completed their studies at UNILAK (Lancang Kuning University). The data attributes used were name, school origin, city of origin, major taken, and student GPA. In this study, a cluster becomes a reference for determining promotional strategies, one of which was the

promotion of regional distribution based on the academic level of students.

Researcher [3] used the Apriori algorithm and the Association Rule as a method in analyzing the relationship between the interests of students of the Nusantara PGRI Kediri University towards a study program and a region, so that it could provide recommendations for promotional areas. The characteristics displayed were the value of support and confidence in the relationship between the department and the student's area of origin, the higher the value of confidence and support, the stronger the value of the relationship between attributes, so that a reference was obtained for campus promotion in each region and the study program that would be highlighted in that area.

In this study, the method used was the Association Rule with the FP-Growth algorithm, where FP-Growth was the development of the Apriori algorithm which was undergoing improvement or development, so that FP-Growth had advantages in terms of accuracy and speed in processing data [1]. In using the Apriori Algorithm, to get a frequent itemset a generate candidate was needed, but in the FP-Growth algorithm the generate candidate was not used, because it required FP-Tree to find frequent itemset [4]. This study would discuss how to implement the FP-Growth algorithm in the promotion strategy at UNAKI Semarang and to get an accurate promotion strategy, where researchers focused more on examining the relationship between variables or items.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this review literature, references were taken from several journals, to support the used concepts through several studies that would support the problem solving at UNAKI Semarang. Some journals that were used as references discussed how to use the FP-Growth algorithm in determining a pattern for making promotional decisions in university.

FP-Growth as an algorithm has also been proven to be carried out in various areas of life, for example in drug sales [5], consumer purchases on woven fabrics [6], hydroponic retail marketing [7], spare parts ordering recommendations [4], a pattern of determination that often appeared in recipient of JAMKESMAS [8], or market basket [9]. Some tertiary institutions specifically used the FP-Growth algorithm to support promotional strategies, such as the STIMIK Triguna Dharma campus [10], where the selected variables included last education, home address, department, and selected study program. At the University of Sorong Victory, it had more concern with observing several variables that were often taken into account by the university, especially the marketing division in the promotion strategy. These variables include advertising, personal selling, and publicity. While at the Dharmas Indonesia University [11], the selected variables were the school's major, the school's origin and the selected study program.

Based on previous research on university promotion strategies, there were a lot of variables has been used, such as student's hometown, elective study program, previous majors in SMA/SMK, or suitable strategies such as advertising, personal selling, even publicity in determining patterns or rules that are used as references in supporting the decision. However, research that used parent work variables was still very little done even though in determining the choice of college admission, parents' work was also influential for it. In this study, researchers added one variable, namely the parents' occupations supporting the promotion strategy at UNAKI Semarang. So that in this study, where the data extracted was much more detailed than previous research, such as data from the student's hometown, preferred study program, previous majors in SMA/SMK, and parents' job as the new added variable to be studied which made the previous research and this research was different. Hopefully, this research could also add to the variety of university promotion research by using the FP-Growth algorithm as a reference in decision making.

A. Data Mining

A process to find or get new correlations of value or meaningful patterns by selecting a large amount of data to be stored in a repository or database, also applying statistical recognition technology patterns and mathematical techniques is the definition of data mining [13].

In processing data mining has stages [4] :

a. Data Cleaning

The new student data obtained from 2016-2018 is quite a lot of data, includes the incomplete data, or repetition in data, or missing data, or the unnecessary data for data processing. For this reason, separating data or removing unnecessary data is called data cleaning.

b. Data Integration

Data integration is the data obtained by identify unique entities from the existing data, such as name, address, school origin, hometown, etc. At this stage, data integration must be carried out carefully, because if there is an error at this stage, then the results obtained can be distorted or even misleading when taking the next action.

c. Data Transformation

At this stage, the previously selected data is changed according to the Data Mining format. Where each data that has been selected is initialized in the form of numbers. In the FP-Growth algorithm, the selected data is converted into binary numbers 0 and 1.

d. Data Mining

All data that has been selected are then processed in the data mining process by applying the FP-Growth algorithm. The result of this process is a grouping of several data that

have the same characteristics, so that they can find patterns or hidden information from the data.

e. Pattern Evaluation

At this stage, the information or pattern generated is tested for correctness, whether the data generated is valid or not. For example, it is true or not true that there is relationship between the previous majors in SMA/SMK with the elective study program.

f. Knowledge Presentation

Based on the results that have been obtained, the next step is to present a new pattern or information obtained where the new pattern or information can answer the problems that have been described earlier.

B. Association Rules

Looking for the frequent itemset in order to find the relationship between items in the dataset is a procedure of the association rule [14]. By using the association rule pattern, it can provide a deeper description of the attributes that often appear in the transaction process.

The basic methodology of association analysis is divided into two stages [15]:

- High Frequency Pattern Analysis

This stage aims to look for item combinations that meet the minimum requirements of the database support value. The support value of an item is obtained by the following formula:

$$Support(A) = \frac{Transaction\ Containing\ A}{Total\ Transaction} \quad (1)$$

In formula (1), it is explained that the carrying value of A is obtained by finding the number of transactions containing A divided by the total transactions.

Table 1: Transaction at Association Rule

Transaction	Itemset
1	A10, B1, C6
2	B1, D12
3	B1, C6
4	A10, B1, D12
5	A10, C6

Explanation :

A10: Central Java
B1 : Accounting

C6 : IPA
D12 : Farmer

In the formula above, the support obtained from the relationship (A10, B1 → C6) is $\frac{1}{5} = 0.2$ or equal to 2%. The value of 1 on support is obtained from itemset A10, B1, C6 amounting to 1 on transaction 1, and the number of transactions is 5.

- Associative Rule Establishment

After all the frequency patterns are found, then find the associative rule that supplies the minimum requirements for confidence to calculate the associative rule confidence A_B. The confidence value of the A_B rule is obtained from the following formula:

$$Confidance = \frac{Total\ Transaction\ Containing\ A\ dan\ B}{Total\ Transaction} \quad (2)$$

The confidance value obtained (A10, B1 → C6) is $\frac{1}{2} = 0.5$ or equal to 5%. The value of 1 of confidence is the same as support, while 2 is obtained from the number of A10 and B1, namely transactions 1 and 4.

C. Frequent Pattern Growth (FP-Growth)

Tree development, or what is commonly called FP-Tree is a concept of the FP-Growth algorithm, which can be used to search for items that appear frequently [14]. The advantage of the FP-Growth algorithm is that it only performs several database scanning times, while the apriori algorithm requires repeated database scanning [4]. Thus, the weaknesses of the Apriori algorithm are fixed by the FP-Growth algorithm [16]. There are three main stages in FP-Growth, namely [15]:

- The stage of generating a Conditional Pattern Base, where in this stage the conditional pattern base generation is obtained through the FP-Tree that has been built previously. At the conditional pattern base stage, the sub database contains a suffix pattern or what is commonly called as *pola akhiran* [5].
- The stages of generating the Conditional FP-Tree, at this stage the support count of each item for the conditional pattern base is added up.
- The stage of Frequent Itemset search, this stage is a single path, then you get frequent itemset by combining items for the FP-Tree conditional.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used here is descriptive research (Description Methods). This method derived patterns (correlation, trend, cluster, territory, and anomaly) which summarized the main relationships in the data [18]. In this study, researchers also used the Association Rule function and the FP-Growth Algorithm. While the application that will be used for testing is RapidMiner [19]. In data collection, researchers did not use a questionnaire, used the obtained data from the Bureau of Student Academic Administration (*Biro Administrasi Akademik Kemahasiswaan/BAAK*) and Marketing Data for the last 3 years, from 2016-2018 at UNAKI Semarang.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Preparation

Researchers used a database application, namely Microsoft Excel 2013 to manage student data from 2016-2018. There

were 10 sample data that was taken from 791 data that have undergone data cleaning, this data could be seen in the example table below.

Table 2. Student Data for 2016 – 2018

No.	NIM	Name	Batch	Hometown
1	121160001	Anita Siti M	2016	Central Java
2	121160002	Cecillia	2016	Central Java
3	121160003	Noerhajati	2016	West Java
4	121160004	Meitry Vidya R	2016	Jakarta
5	121160005	Francesca . F	2016	Jakarta
6	121160006	Christopher A.R	2016	Central Java
7	121160007	Albert Hans P	2016	West Kalimantan
8	121160008	Najib Ali M	2016	West Java
9	121160009	Shelly Septiana	2016	North Sumatera
10	121160010	Lucky Budi .U	2016	Central Java

The data that has been obtained could not be processed immediately, because the data that has been collected was selected based on the required attributes such as Hometown, Preferred Study Program, previous majors in SMA/SMK, and Parents' Job. The attributes that have been selected were transformed and given a code first to make it easier in processing Data Mining on each itemset.

Table 3. Attribute Encoding Table

Code	Explanation
A	Howntown
B	Preffered Study Program
C	Previous Majors in SMA/SMK
D	Parents' Job

Table 4. Encoding Table

Code	Explanation
A1	ACEH
A2	BALI
A3	BANTEN
A4	BATAM
A5	BENGKULU
A6	YOGYAKARTA
A7	JAKARTA
A8	JAMBI
A9	WEST JAVA
A10	CENTRAL JAVA
A11	EAST JAVA
A12	WEST KALIMANTAN
A13	CENTRAL KALIMANTAN
A14	EAST KALIMANTAN
A15	NORTH KALIMANTAN
A16	LAMPUNG
A17	MALUKU
A18	WEST NUSA TENGGARA
A19	EAST NUSA TENGGARA
A20	PAPUA
A21	WEST PAPUA
A22	RIAU
A23	WEST SULAWESI BARAT
A24	NORTH SULAWESI
A25	WEST SUMATERA
A26	SOUTH SUMATERA
A27	NORTH SUMATERA
B1	ACCOUNTING
B2	MANAGEMENT
B3	TAXATION
B4	PSYCHOLOGY
B5	ENGLISH LITERATURE
B6	INFORMATION SYSTEM
B7	TECHNICAL INFORMATION
C1	OFFICE ADMINISTRATION

C2	ACCOUNTING
C3	ANIMATION
C4	LANGUAGE
C5	ELECTRONIC
C6	SCIENCE
C7	SOCIAL SCIENCE
C8	MULTIMEDIA
C9	AUTOMOTIVE
C10	MARKETING
C11	BANKING
C12	HOSPITALITY
C13	AGRICULTURE
C14	SOFTWARE ENGINEERING
C15	CULINARY ART
C16	ELECTRIC POWER INSTALLATION ENGINEERING
C17	TECHNICAL LIGHT VEHICLE
C18	COMPUTER AND NETWORK ENGINEERING
C19	RADIO BROADCASTING PRODUCTION ENGINEERING
D1	TOXOLOGIST
D2	LABOR
D3	LECTURER
D4	HOUSEWIFE
D5	GENERAL EMPLOYEES
D6	MANAGER
D7	FISHERMAN
D8	MERCHANT
D9	PASTOR
D10	NEWSPAPER SELLER
D11	RETIRED CIVIL SERVANT
D12	FARMER
D13	CATTLEMAN
D14	CIVIL SERVANT
D15	POLICE
D16	DRIVER
D17	PEDICAB DRIVER
D18	ENTREPRENEUR

At this stage, the dataset consisting of 791 data records would be determined by the variable value in the form of a binary number, where the selected data would be 1 and data that was not selected would be 0 and so on until the process finished. See the table below.

Table 5. Student data after being converted in binary form

TID	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

After the student data has been converted, then the selected items were sorted into the table as below.

Tabel 6. Frequent Items

TID	ITEM
1	A10,B1,C7,D12
2	A10,B1,C7,D18
3	A9,B1,C8,D14
4	A7,B1,C1,D12
5	A7,B1,C7,D9
6	A10,B1,C6,D18
7	A12,B1,C7,D12
8	A9,B1,C6,D9
9	A27,B1,C6,D5
10	A10,B1,C7,D12
11	A10,B1,C7,D12
12	A14,B1,C6,D9
13	A27,B1,C18,D9
14	A27,B1,C7,D9
15	A12,B1,C6,D14
16	A5,B1,C6,D12
17	A10,B1,C7,D9
18	A5,B1,C6,D9
19	A9,B1,C6,D5
20	A10,B1,C7,D9
21	A10,B1,C7,D9
22	A5,B1,C6,D2
23	A10,B1,C14,D9
24	A27,B1,C18,D4
25	A11,B1,C6,D14
26	A9,B1,C6,D9
27	A12,B1,C6,D9
28	A9B1,C6,D4
29	A11,B1,C7,D5
30	A12,B1,C6,D12

A7	9
A26	9
C19	9
D8	9
A14	8
A21	7
C17	6
A15	5
C9	5
A6	4
A8	4
D1	4
D11	4
D15	4
A2	3
A17	3
C10	3
C13	3
C15	3
D3	3
A1	2
A4	2
A23	2
A24	2
C3	2
C5	2
C16	2
D6	2
D7	2
A3	1
A18	1
C11	1
C12	1
D10	1
D13	1
D17	1

In the table below, the researcher recorded the appearance of the items in order of the highest frequency.

Table 7. The appearance of an item based on the highest frequent

ITEM	TOTAL
A10	362
C6	338
C7	276
D12	189
B7	179
B1	160
D9	144
B5	127
D18	118
D5	117
A12	114
B2	101
D14	94
B3	91
B6	73
A27	60
B4	60
D4	43
D2	40
A16	35
C18	28
C1	27
C8	27
A9	26
A13	23
A20	22
A25	22
C4	22
C2	20
A11	19
A22	17
C14	15
A19	13
D16	12
A5	10

Item that had a frequency above support count ≥ 50 ($551/3154 = 0.1$) are A10, C6, C7, D12, B7, B1, D9, B5, D18, D5, A12, B2, D14, B3, B6, A27, and B4. These seventeen itemset would be processed into the FP-Tree.

Table 8. Dataset Based on the Most High Frequent

TID	ITEM
1	A10,C7, D12,B1
2	A10, C7,B1,D18
3	B1, D14
4	D12,B1
5	C7,B1,D9
6	A10,C6,B1,D18
7	C7,D12,B1,A12
8	C6,B1,D9
9	C6,B1,D5, A27
10	A10,C7, D12,B1
11	A10,C7, D12,B1
12	C6,B1,D9
13	B1,D9, A27
14	C7,B1,D9, A27
15	C6,B1,A12, D14
16	C6,D12, B1
17	A10 ,C7, B1,D9
18	C6,B1,D9
19	C6,B1,D5
20	A10 ,C7, B1,D9
21	A10 ,C7, B1,D9
22	C6,B1
23	A10,B1,D9
24	B1, A27
25	C6,B1, D14
26	C6,B1,D9
27	C6,B1,D9,A12
28	C6,B1
29	C7,B1,D5

Picture 13. The path that had suffix A10

After searching for frequent itemset ending in B2, A12, D9, D12, D18, D5, C6, C7 and A10, then the results were summarized into a table which then contained the Conditional Pattern Base and the Conditional FP-Tree as below.

Table 9. Forming Conditional Pattern Base and Conditional FP-Tree

Suffix	Conditional Pattern Base	Conditional FP-Tree
B1	{(A10,C6):1, (A10,C7):2, (A10,C7,D12):1, (A10):1, (D12):1, (C7):1, (C7,D12):1, (C6):1, (C6,D12):1}	{(A10:4, C6:3, C7:4, D12:4)} (A10,C6,C7,D12)
A12	{(C7,D12,B1):1, (C6,B1):1, (C6,B1,D9):1, (C6,D12,B1):1}	{(C7:1, D12:2, B1:4, C6:3, D9:1)} (C7,D12,B1,C6,D9)
D9	{(A10,C7,B1):1, (A10,B1):1, (C7,B1):1, (C6,B1):1}	{(A10:2, C7:2, B1:4, C6:1)} (A10, C7, B1, C6)
D12	{(A10,C7):1, (C7):1, (C6):1}	{(A10:1, C7:2, C6:1)} (A10,C7,C6)
D18	{(A10,C6,B1):1, (A10,C7,B1):1}	{(A10:2, C6:1, B1:2, C7:1)} (A10, C6, B1, C7)
D5	{(C7,B1):1, (C6,B1):1}	{(C7:1, B1:2, C6:1)} (C7,B1,C6)
C6	{(A10:1)}	{(A10:1)} (A10)
C7	{(A10:1)}	{(A10:1)} (A10)
A10		

After obtaining the conditional pattern base and conditional FP-Tree, the next step was to calculate the value of support and confidence. In order to achieve high accuracy, a minimum confidence ≥ 0.6 was set.

Table 10. Frequent itemsets that meet the Minimum Support Value ≥ 0.1 and Confidence ≥ 0.6

No	X	Y	Support	Confidence
1	C7,B7	A10	0.04	0.65
2	C6,D5	A10	0.04	0.66
3	A10,B7,D5	C6	0.02	0.66
4	C6,B7	A10	0.07	0.67
5	B7	A10	0.15	0.67
6	D12,B7	A10	0.02	0.67

7	C7,D18	A10	0.03	0.70
8	B7,D14	A10	0.02	0.81
9	B7,D5	A10	0.03	0.83
10	C6,B7,D5	A10	0.02	0.90

From the rules that have been formed above, the result of association rule pattern was as follows:

1. If the previous major in SMA/SMK was Science and the Informatics Engineering study program was selected as preferred study program, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 65%
2. If the previous department was in SMA/SMK IPA and the parents' job was private employees, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 66%
3. If the area of origin was Central Java, the study program selected was informatics engineering as preferred study program and the work of parents of private employees, then the previous major in SMA/SMK was Science with a confidence value of 66%
4. If the previous major in SMA / SMK was Sciences and the study program selected was Informatics Engineering as preferred study program, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 67%
5. If the informatics engineering study program was selected as preferred study program, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 67%
6. If the parents' job was a farmer and the choice of study program was informatics engineering, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 67%
7. If the previous major in SMA/SMK was Science and the parents' job was self-employed, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 70%
8. If the selected study program was informatics engineering and the parents's job was civil servants, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 81%
9. If the selected study program was informatics engineering and the parents' job was private employees, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 83%
10. If the previous department was in IPA SMA / SMK, the selected study program was informatics engineering as preferred study program and the parents' job was private employees, then the area of origin was Central Java with a confidence value of 90%

The most accurate support and confidence values of the 10 rules generated above were a combination (C6, B7, D5) {IPA, Informatics Engineering, Private Employees} which had a support value of 2% and a confidence value of 90%. From the 10 rules above, it was expected that they could be used as a rule or pattern in determining an effective and efficient promotion strategy at UNAKI Semarang

V. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

From the 791 data records that have passed the process of cleaning, the data stored in Microsoft Excel with file name **datatesis.xls**, then it would be tested using Rapidminer 9.3.001 software. The dataset consisting of 791 records containing item of 1 and 0 was saved into Microsoft Excel with the name **datatesis.xls** and then the data would be imported into rapidminer. See the table below.

Row No.	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12	A13	A14	A15	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Picture 14. Combination Table

Then, the next step was the process of connecting FP-Growth and Association Rules in the rapidminer where FP-Growth was located in the first res and the Association Rules located in the second res by setting the minimum support and minimum confidence in advance.

Picture 15. Rapidminer Design Interface

After running, the following rules are obtained :

No.	Premises	Conclusion	Support	Confidence	Lift
7	C7, B7	A10	0.043	0.654	1.429
8	C6, D5	A10	0.042	0.660	1.442
9	A10, B7, D5	C6	0.025	0.667	1.560
10	C6, B7	A10	0.076	0.674	1.473
11	B7	A10	0.153	0.676	1.477
12	D12, B7	A10	0.029	0.676	1.478
13	C7, D18	A10	0.035	0.700	1.530
14	B7, D14	A10	0.028	0.815	1.780
15	B7, D5	A10	0.038	0.833	1.821
16	C6, B7, D5	A10	0.025	0.909	1.986

Picture 16. Display lift ratio > 1 with rapidminer

In the association rule, lift ratio was an important parameter besides support and confidence. The lift ratio was to measure how important the rules were based on the value of support and confidence. The lift ratio was the validity of the transaction process and provides information on whether product A was purchased together with product B. The valid rule was if the lift ratio was >1.

To get the Lift Ratio, it could be calculated by the formula:

$$\frac{\text{Support}(A \cap B)}{\text{Support} A * \text{Support} B} =$$

From Picture 16 which shown that the combination (C6, B7, D5) {Science, Informatics Engineering, Private Employees}, the Lift Ratio was >1 and the result could be said valid. So it could be counclude that if the previous department in SMASMK was Science, informatics engineering was selected as preferred study program and the parents’s job was private employees, then the hometown was Central Java with a confidence value of 90% and a support value of 2% of the overall data.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on results of the analysis and testing that has been done, the conclusions of this study were:

FP-Growth was an algorithm that was more accurate and efficient in generating patterns or rules from the sample data for new student candidates at UNAKI Semarang. Where in finding the Frequent Itemset using the development tree or FP-Tree of items that often appear, variable data was also very influential in determining the level of accuracy and the amount of the minimum support and minimum confidence values.

For example, of the pattern of relationships from previous majors in SMA/SMK, preferred study program and parent's job, if the previous department in SMA/SMK was Science, the study program of choice was informatics engineering and the parents’s job was private employees, then the hometown was Central Java with a support value of 0.02, which meant The percentage of appearance of an itemset in forming the number of rules was less than or equal to 2% and a confidence value of 0.90. This meant that the level of confidence of the rule or pattern formed was at least 90% and a maximum of 100% and the higher the resulting confidence value, the better it was in determine the promotion strategy. From the 10 rules generated, hopefully that they could become a reference for UNAKI Semarang in carrying out targeted promotions in the future.

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